

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A480

17 September 1996

OXICOA — TACIA

ADDENDUM

The correct dates for each of the flights
are as follows:-

475	9	September	1996
476	10	September	1996
477	11	September	1996
478	13	September	1996
479	16	September	1996
480	17	September	1996
481	19	September	1996

TACIA OXICOA AUG-SEPT 96 Flight Summary

Prepared by: Andrew Kaye and Hannah Richer

[1] A475 9/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 1 2 hr 40 min

A short test flight for the chemistry instrumentation was carried out. The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). After initial concerns about the NO background, the NO_x instrument was found to operate satisfactorily on the two available channels (NO and NO₂).

An anticyclone centred to the west of the UK provided possible TACIA type weather. However, delays, due to incomplete airworthiness certification, meant that there was insufficient time to search for plumes from the UK. However, a small local plume was encountered in the Bristol Channel (51.36N, 4.12E).

Data from this flight could possibly be used to validate emission data from South Wales.

[2] A476 10/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 2 4 hr 30 min

Instruments performed as in the previous test flight: The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). The NO background had improved and the NO_x instrument was generally found to operate well on the two channels (NO and NO₂). However, on reaching maximum altitude difficulties were encountered on controlling the flow rate in the NO₂ channel.

A persistent anticyclone centred to the west of the UK again provided TACIA type conditions. However, delays, due to instrument requirements, meant that there was limited time to search for plumes from the UK. However, cross wind runs were carried out at an interval of approximately 60 miles along the SW coast. Trajectory analysis is to be carried out to determine whether the same air mass was sampled twice. However, no particularly notable plumes could be distinguished from the ozone, carbon monoxide and formaldehyde data. However, useful background information was obtained.

[3] A477 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 00 min

The presence of an occluded frontal system over Norway/North Sea facilitated the study of three different airmasses.

Profiles were successfully flown on both sides of the warm front, but there was not sufficient time to travel to the northern edge of the cold frontal surface. However the lowest levels of the second stack may have been north of the front.

Ozone, formaldehyde and PAN instruments worked well, but the CO background problem was not corrected and the NO_x NO₂ channel flow problem had not been resolved.

[4] A478 11/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 3 2 hr 56 min

Thursday 12 September was used to install the NO_y converters and rectify the CO instrument. The CO work was successful. However the NO_y converters took longer than expected to complete. This resulted in a delayed take off.

Although primarily a TACIA instrument test flight the opportunity was taken to characterise the Arctic Maritime air mass over the North Sea. This effectively completed the work started on A477.

The chemistry kit performed as well as could be expected given the reduced warm up times available. The ozone pump switched off unexpectedly during the flight which caused a loss of data until the problem was identified.

[5] A479 11/9/96 TACIA 5 hr 40 min

There was a high pressure centred over the North Sea on this day which gave rise to continental outflow in

the south-west approaches.

A very successful trial of the TACIA flying pattern, with two stacks being flown to sample continental air. A double inversion (875 and 950 mbar) was identified effectively capping pollutants and isolating them from the ocean surface sinks. Elevated levels of aerosol, CO (170 ppb), NO (40 ppt), NO₂ (400 ppt) and O₃ (65 ppb) were noted in this layer. Another interesting parcel of air was also sampled at higher altitudes (6 - 8 km). This air parcel was characterised by high levels of CO and aerosol. All the chemistry instrumentation performed well and the flight will provide a valuable contribution to the TACIA experiment.

[6] A480 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 04 min

An anticyclone was centred to the north of the North Sea, such that continental plumes from northern Europe were reaching southern England across the North Sea. The same anticyclone was investigated during flight A479, at which time the high was centred over the UK.

The aim of this flight was to characterise air parcels within the anticyclone: both air parcels with recent continental influence and those with mainly marine back trajectories were studied. The highest pollutant concentrations of the campaign were measured during this flight in the boundary layer near Boscombe Down and in the marine boundary layer in the southern North Sea.

The marine boundary layer was distinct from the rest of the troposphere by a low level inversion. A slightly higher inversion was also apparent in profiles carried out north of 54 N. Interestingly, the seemingly typical vertical structure was not found in the southern North Sea: only the marine inversion was present.

A plume was encountered in the marine boundary layer at the first sampling region and elevated NO_x, NO_y and CO were observed with a corresponding decrease in ozone, indicating recent anthropogenic inputs. Profiles throughout the lowest 6000 ft of the atmosphere, whilst travelling northward, indicated some chemically aged parcels of air with elevated ozone, CO and NO_y. Haze layers were also visible. However, most of the air was generally clean. Further North, haze layers were less frequent, but layers with elevated ozone were still apparent. Elevated CO with a corresponding decrease in ozone indicated some recent pollution in the marine boundary layer at 57.2 N and 0.8 E.

All the chemistry instruments performed well during the flight. In particular, the peroxide measurements were found to show similar features to the calculated peroxide. Pitch, roll and yaw manoeuvres were carried out in order to test the NO_x inlets: preliminary results indicated that there were no large effects.

[7] A481 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight/NOXY test 6 hr 16 min

An attempt was made at an airmass characterization flight. However, within an hour of take off, the peroxide and CO instruments had failed completely and the NO_x was only functioning at 50%. After consultation with the instrument operators it was decided that useful tests could still be carried with the operational NO_x channels and the flight plan was changed to a NO_x test flight. Several NILU and MRF bottles were also filled for analysis of hydrocarbons and possibly CO.

However, it is interesting to note that, at one point, air of stratospheric origin was encountered: we were frustrated by the lack of a complete suite of instruments. Recently polluted air and air which was chemically aged, as indicated by ratios of NO_x/NO_y and ozone, were both sampled. Useful data on emissions from north eastern Europe may have been gained.

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 480

DATE: 17/9/96

Take off: 10:21:52 Z

Landing: 16:22:33 Z

Aircraft Scientist : H RICKER
Flight Leader : M RULE
Others CLOUD PH. : M PICKERING
NOXY. K DEWEY/S BAGVITE
PEROXIDE: B BANDI/L CARDINAS
PAN/OZONE: J. KENT
CO : S KESSLER
BOTTLES D TIDDEMAN
+ A KAYE
+ P MONKS

Captain : M. PURSE
Co-pilot : C. O'BRIEN
Navigator : J. AYRES
Engineer : K. QUICK
Loadmaster : J. CANNING.

(17)

Trials Instructions TACIA
Operating area : Southern North Sea.

General synoptic situation

TIME :

ACSOE / TACIA Campaign

A480 17th September, 1996

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
102152		Take off from BOSCOMBE		
103354 (13)	-105015 (14)	Run 1	FL100	060 deg
110045 (15)	-112446 (19)	Profile P1	FL200->50ft	110/040 deg
112644 (20)	-113037 (21)	Run 2.1	600ft	210 deg
113037 (21)	-113538 (22)	Run 2.2	600ft	210 deg
113631 (23)	-114053 (24)	Profile P2	600ft->2800ft	030 deg
114319 (25)	-114823 (26)	Run 3	2500ft	215 deg
114958 (27)	-115410 (28)	Profile P3	2500ft->5000ft	035 deg
115410 (28)	-115918 (29)	Run 4	5000ft	035 deg
120016 (30)	-121100 (33)	Profile P4	5000ft->FL150	030 deg
121100 (33)	-121603 (34)	Run 5.1	FL150	030 deg
121603 (34)	-122021 (35)	Run 5.2	FL150	030 deg
Special Manouveres				
123623 (36)	-123728 (37)	Run 6.1, low pitch	FL120	330 deg
123838 (38)	-123939 (39)	Run 6.2, high pitch	FL120	330 deg
124156 (40)	-124252 (41)	Run 6.3, sideslip	FL120 r wing dwn	330 deg
124314 (42)	-124414 (43)	Run 6.4, sideslip	FL120 l wing dwn	330 deg
124730 (44)	-124803 (45)	Run 6.5, sideslip	FL120 r wing dwn	330 deg
Sawtooths				
124903 (46)	-130521 (50)	Profile P5	FL120->50ft	070/025 deg
130521 (50)	-131742 (53)	Profile P6	50ft->6000ft	025/330 deg
131742 (53)	-132124 (54)	Run 7	6000ft	330 deg
132124 (54)	-133042 (55)	Profile P7	6000ft->600ft	330 deg
133042 (55)	-134538 (57)	Profile P8	600ft->FL100	330 deg
134734 (58)	-140343 (62)	Profile P9	FL100->50ft	330/205 deg
140549 (63)	-141044 (64)	Run 8.1	600ft	205 deg
141044 (64)	-141604 (66)	Run 8.2	600ft	205 deg
141715 (66)	-142231 (67)	Profile P10	600ft->FL30	035 deg
142231 (67)	-142742 (68)	Run 9	FL29	045 deg
142742 (68)	-143422 (69)	Profile P11	FL29->FL60	045 deg
143553 (70)	-144100 (71)	Run 10	FL50	210 deg
144100 (71)	-145224 (74)	Profile P12	FL50->FL150	040 deg
145335 (75)	-145839 (76)	Run 11.1	FL150	210 deg
145839 (76)	-150350 (77)	Run 11.2	FL150	210 deg
150350 (77)	-150827 (78)	Profile P13	FL150->FL200	210 deg
160142 (79)	-161103 (81)	Profile P14	FL100->2300ft	240 deg
162233		Land at BOSCOMBE		

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<p style="text-align: center;">1 9 1 1</p>	<p>Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 1 4 2</p>	<p>Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 1</p>	<p>SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEMOS log EC9C Chemistry log (bottle sampler)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">6 2 1</p>	<p>Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">✓ ✓ ✓ ✓</p>	<p>Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track</p>

A480 17-SEP-96 10:33:54-16:11:03GMT

A480 17-SEP-96 Height time series

OXICOA VI: Air Mass Characterization Experiment

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

To characterize the atmospheric chemical composition of the airmass. The data collected will be added to a systematically collected airmass data base. The data base will be used to determine the oxidising capacity and the budget of tropospheric oxidants in marine air at mid latitudes in the northern hemisphere..

LOCATION: North Sea

WEATHER: Typically tropical and polar maritime air reaching the UK.

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Boscombe Down and transit to sampling area at convenient altitude.
 - [1.1] Hold climb at 3000 ft for wet chemistry check.
 - [1.2] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed not critical) for NO_x Calibration.
- [2] Profile descent from approx. FL200 at 1000ft/min to approx. FL¹⁰⁰~~70~~ then 500ft/min to minimum safe altitude.
- [3] Execute a stepped profile in same area as descent profile, at levels specified by aircraft scientist. 5 minute runs.

600ft, 2800ft, 5000ft, FL150, _____, _____, _____.

- [4] Transit to new area and repeat [2] & [3] as time permits

_____, _____, _____, _____, _____, _____, _____.

_____, _____, _____, _____, _____, _____, _____.

- [5] Transit back to Boscombe Down as convenient.
 - [5.1] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed not critical) for NO_x Calibration.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure to be kept constant on level runs.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H. RICHER

Project: ^{ALICE} MUSE

Date: 17/9/96

Flight No: A480 Page 1 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
								TAKE OFF BOSCOMBE DOWN	
10:25:54	12		2000ft			51.40	-1.61	WET CHEM CHECK	
10:27:52			6000ft		357			ASCENT 1/8 SMALL CU INVERSION 900 _{M6} HAZE NOTABLE CO 100 PPB O ₃ 47 PPB	
10:31:18			9000ft		358	51.78	-1.69	SECOND SMALL INVERSION 740 METER.	
10:33:54	13		10,000ft		51	51.96	-1.54	START 15 MIN RUN FOR CALIBRATION	
10:37:00					50	52.05	-1.31	CUMULUS INCREASING 6/8 4/8 CIRROS ABOVE SOME O ₃ PEAKS NOTED UP TO 58	
10:47:51			10,000ft		67	52.48	-0.22	O ₃ UP TO CA. 60 PPB CO GRADUAL INC. TO 125 PPB	
10:50:15	14		10,000ft		98	52.57	0.12	CHANGE HEADING & START ASCENT O ₃ DEC TOWARD END OF RUN	
								O ₃ & CO ANTICORRELATION ON ASCENT DEWPOINT & O ₃ CORRELATION UNCHANG	
								LAYER BETWEEN FL100 - FL120 O ₃ & CO ANTICORRELATION FL090 → FL120.	
11:00:45	15	P1	20,000ft		105	52.45	1.09	FL098 FL138) START OF DESCENT	
			17,000ft		100	52.42	1.31	OVER COAST	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H. R. CHER

Project: ACSUE Date: 17/9/76

Flight No: A480 Page 2 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
								V. SLIGHT INVERSION 650 mb above 850	
								V. SLIGHT INVERSION 800 mbar 800	
11:17:50								WINDS CHANGE	
			6000ft			52.35		60 INTERRUPT PROFILE	
						2.32			
11:14:26	17					52.37			
						2.34			
11:20:06						52.61		NOx 2 PPA	
						2.53		2 PPA NO2 IN BOUNDARY LAYER.	
11:24:36	18		50ft			52.80		ALTIMETER READING 1027	
						2.68			
11:25:27	19	18 EPP	600ft			52.8		NOx readings high	
						2.7		O3 76 PPA CO 109 PPA	
11:26:44	20	R2.1				52.75		O3	
						2.72		CALIBRATIONS / ZERO AT BEGIN OF RUN	
11:30:37	21	R2.2				52.58		END CAL START RUN	
						2.60			
11:35:06		R2.2	600ft			52.39		ELEVATED CO ELEVATED NOx	
						2.43		REDUCED O3 AEROSOL VARIABLE 900	

-100
COUNTS

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG
 Aircraft Scientist: H RICHARD

Project: *ALSOE* Date: 17/9/96
 Flight No: A480 Page 3 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
	22	R 2.2					END OF RUN 2.2		
	23	P2	1700ft		32			START OF PROFILE P2	
11:40:53	24	P2	2800ft			52.6 2.6		END OF PROFILE P2	
11:43:19	25	R 2.2	2800ft		210	52.56 2.63		JUST BELOW SMALL CU START RUN CO 130 O ₂ 38	
						52.41 2.45		JUST IN CLOUD	
11:48:27	26	R 3.2	2700ft			52.34 2.37		HAD TO GO DOWN TO AVOID CLOUD, CO PEAK. END OF RUN	
11:49:	27	P3	2500ft		32	52.30 2.39		PROFILE	
11:51:00					27	52.33 2.40		CO LEVELS RAPIDLY RETURNING TO "NORMAL" ~120 PPB	
11:54:00			4700ft			52.49 2.70		O ₂ INCREASING ABOVE CLOUD 55 PPB NO DOWN TO 50 PPT	
11:54:10	28	R 4.2	5000ft		26	52.56 2.55		CO CM NOXY ZERO.	
11:59:18	29	R 4.2				52.74 2.67		END RUN.	
12:00:16	30	P4			201	52.72 2.60		1000ft/mib.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H. RICHER

Project: AC50E Date: 17/9/196
 Flight No: A480 Page 4 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						12:05:08			
12:07:59	31	P4	11			52.35	2.35	INTERUPT OF PROFILE	
12:09:03	32							RESTART PROFILE	
12:11:00	33	R5.4	FL150		28	52.45	2.48	END PROFILE START. ^{U.INDOFR/9} CO LOW 95PPB O ₃ 50 ^{deg MIS}	
12:16	34	R5.2						LOW CAL RUN	
12:20:21	35					52.95	2.87	END OF RUN	
12:24:27						53.06	2.62	DESCEND TO FL120. MAX SPEED OUT OF CONTROLLED REGION	
12:36:23	36	R6.1	FL120		318	53.81	1.33	MANOEUVRES LOW PITCH	
12:37:28	37	END	"		318	53.81	1.26	END	
12:38:38	38	R6.2	"			53.8	1.18	HIGH PITCH (EFFECT NOTED ON NOOY)	
12:39:39	39	END	"		322	52.94	1.13	END	
12:41:56	40	R6.3	FL120			54.03	1.12	SIDE SLIP	

PILOT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACSOE Date: 12/19/96
 Flight No: A480 Page 5 of 9

Aircraft Scientist: K RICHER

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rid	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:41	41	END 63	FL120					END SLIP SLIDE SIDE SLIP RIGHT	
12:43:40	42	R64				54.09	1.26	SIDE SLIP LEFT	
12:44:14	43	END R64	FL120		64	54.09	1.36	END SIDE SLIP LEFT	
12:47:30	44	65				54.22	1.62		
12:38:03	45	END				54.23	1.65		
12:49:03	46	P5	FL120		65	54.26	1.75	PROFILE 1000 ft/min.	
12:54:30	47					54.39	2.16	NOx inc. 100 NO2 (37x mbw)	
12:55:54						54.42	2.25	INVERSION 800 mbw. (879 mbw).	
12:58:09						54.48	2.39	INC. NOx J	
12:59:09	48	P5	3000ft FL120			54.51	2.52	CHANGE TO 500 ft/min	
12:59:36	49	"			16	54.56	2.54		
		P6							

SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H Richer

Project: ACSOE Date: 17/4/96
Flight No: A480 Page 6 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:07:	S1	P6							
13:08:08	S2	P6			327			REPEATED SAWTOOTH FROM SECOND SAMPLING REGION.	
						55.28		PASSAGE THROUGH INVERSION PICKED OUT BY H ₂ O ₂	
						2.20			
13:17:42	S3	END P6 RUN 7			329	55.51		HAZE LAYER JUST ABOVE BL	
						1.92			
13:21:24	S4	END P7	600ft			55.56		START OF PORPOISE DOWN	
						1.85			
13:22:00			550ft			55.63		OZONE INC. (MAX 55 PPB) (SOME NO _x INC)	
						1.76		CORRESPONDING CO INC. (115-130 PPB)	
13:26:00	S5		260ft			55.81		OZONE DEC. ON APPROACHING CLOUD LAYER (500 ft/min)	
						1.52			
	S5	END P7.	600ft			56.08		(500 ft min.)	
13	S6					56.41		V. CLEAN AIR (HAVING PREVIOUSLY NOTED A HAZE LAYER)	
						0.76		O ₃ ~ 40 PPB CO ₂ ~ 100 PPD	
13:41:51			600ft		326	56.50		INVERSION FZS Nbr	
						0.65		CO, O ₃ ANTICORRELATION? NO _x inc.	
13:45:38	S7	END P8	FL100		326	56.71			
						0.38			
13:47:34	S8	P9.	FL100		33	56.81		1000 ft/min.	
						0.34			

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H. RICHAR

Project: ACSUE Date: 17/9/96

Flight No: A480 Page 7 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:48:00		P9				57	0.6	OZONE CONC'S MIRRORED ON DESCENT. INVERSION CENTRED 800 mbar.	
								3 PEAKS AT 6400 ft.	
13:53:35	59		4000ft		40	57.12	0.66	CHANGE RATE DESCENT. RIGS & SHIP NOTED.	
13:55:54						57.22	0.78	INVERSION 900 mbar. ^{O3 DEC.} HAZE NOTED & AEROSOL INC., CO INC 130PPB	
13:57:15			2000ft					CLOUD (CUMULUS SMALL).	
13:59:29	60		1000ft		205	57.39	0.97	INTERUPT: CHANGE HEADING	
14:00	61		700ft			57.25	0.84	RIGS & SHIPS.	
14:03:43	62		50ft		195	57.23	0.52	RIGS & SHIPS. SEA STATE 4	
	63	R8.1	600ft					CALIBRATION ZERO.	
14:10:14	64	R8.2			201	56.92	0.52		
			2700ft						

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A480 Date: 17.9.96 User: H. RICHK
Interactive by: M. ROLF
Date: 18.9.96

Renav

Kalman Filtering applied

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

$$a = - 0.4119 \text{ E} + 1$$

$$b = + 0.2789 \text{ E} - 2$$

$$c = + 0.5151 \text{ E} - 6$$

LWC

✓ Nothing much in way of lwc from
Johnson Williams

Heimann / Barnes

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A480 Date: 17.9.96 A/S Name: H. RICHER

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for³.....

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project~~FA~~ AC SOE.....

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long?10 years.....

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?.....

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A480 Date: 17.9.96

Page...of 1

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0825	REF +	5	567			Approx	0568
	REF -	7	2856			Approx	2858
	AOSS	19	4095	PORT F/S STBD O/S	TORQUE 2.0		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	4095	UP F/S DOWN O/S	TORQUE 3.5		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	0			As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	3862	998	999/0.3	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3974	→ 1000			
	A/S	9	84			As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1117	345			
	UP2S	82	993	167			
	UIRS	83	434	JND2			
	UP1Z	84	150	✓		Approx	0147
	UP2Z	85	145	✓		Approx	0149
	UIRZ	86	432	—		Approx	2061
	UP1T	87	2549	+14	+14.6	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2552	—		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0	—		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	295	56			
	LP2S	92		271 - 31			
	LIRS	93	4095	53			
	LP1Z	94		151 ✓		Approx	0150
	LP2Z	95	0829	Read Similar	155 ✓	Approx	0146
	LIRZ	96		53		Approx	2050
	LP1T	97	5484	18	+14.7	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2444	✓		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0	.		As IAT	
	J/W	42	996	0.0	✓	As Indicated	0000
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	2874	12.5	12.6		
	HYCC	59	720	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	/	OFF		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139					
	DTF	10	579	+16			
	DTC	11	6				
	NDTF	23	3665			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5	14			
	INCT	48					
	SCN	140	2623/	2392		less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2620			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	115			0640-1860	< min
	O3	100	69				
	O3P	106	1997			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1438				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	480	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	083	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	545	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	10			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4094			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: on the pan.

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0936	TWCD	70	2609	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1075	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	119	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2391	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2245	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2059			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2111			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1025			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089			4095	
	EV1V	170	2043				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3430				
	EVIC	173	3968				
	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	(OFF) On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon JNC 2		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	(OFF) On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon JNC 2		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A480 Date: 17.9.96

Page!...of 1

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1026	REF +	5	567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2855	✓		Approx 3071 2858	
	AOSS	19	1957	Noisy F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1669	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095	FL55		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3161	817/5.8	FL58 ✓	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3910	987.			
	A/S	9	2363	243	✓	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	1809.	594	593		
	UP2S	82	1594	289	322		
	UIRS	83	746	JN02			
	UPIZ	84	155	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	152	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	746			Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2562	+14	+17	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2575			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	430.	111	110		
	LP2S	92	435	72	67		
	UIRS	93	175	JN02			
	LP1Z	94	153	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	162	✓		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	183			Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2572	+13		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2546			As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0			As IAT	
	J/W	42	1190	0.0		As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	1770	-22			
	HYCC	59	1093	C		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1015			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	931				
	DTF	10	2488				
	DTC	11	5	+8	+9		
	NDTF	23	2177			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5	+8			
	INCT	48					
	CON	140	2825	/2392		less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	1402	✓		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1390	✓		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	161				
	O3P	106	1958			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1815				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	480	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	103	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	441	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	13			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
—————							
	LATC	160	Dec	591		51.9	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4078		-1.51	Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL100

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
103S	TWCD	70	1359	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2518	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1409	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2712	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2241	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2705	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1533	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1019	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	3476	✓			
	EV2V	171	3132	✓			
	NPWR	172	2697	✓			
	EVIC	173	4019	✓			
	EV2C	174	4004	✓			

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 17.9.96 Flight No. A480

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VIDEO TAPE

No. A480 #1

Ends 1330

- DFC
- RFC
- FFC

	GPS	INU
Lat.	52°09.95 N	52°10.78
Long.	1°10.86W	1°09.73
Time	103910	103925

DRS

recording to HORACE

HORACE

recording to optical disk

SATCOM

sending position reports

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		%ms ⁻¹
07435		START	RECORDING				GPS	pan	51'	09.90	N
							Position	-	001'	44.65	E
0930		Set	INU to NAVIGATE								
102152		TAKE OFF	FROM BOSCOMBE								
103246		Start	Video								
			START RUN 1								
103354	13	FL100	—	060	230	274	0.3	-10.3			115/8
			END RUN 1								
105015	14	FL100	—	075	230						
105110			cabin climbing								
105150			good cloud streets on FFC								
			climb to FL200								
			START PROFILE P1							1000ft/min	
110045	15	FL200	—	110	190	262	-20.8	-31			
			cabin descending								
111350			cabin pressure stable 1032								
			INTERRUPT PROFILE P1								
111356	16	FL60	—	090							
111426	17	FL60	—	035	180	195	4.6	-23.5	OFF		098/16
111647	18	FL40									
			reduce r.o.d. to 500ft/min								
			END PROFILE P1								
112446	19	50ft	1023	040							5

Flies

Video Tape ok? 1330

TIME GMT	EVENT NO	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.			
				START	RUN	2.1.		zero	run			
112644	20	600ft	1023.	210	180	185	12.1	7.0			082/8.	
				END	RUN 2.1	/	START RUN 2.2					
113037	21	600ft	1023	210	180.	184	12.0					
				END	RUN	2.2						
113538	22.	600ft	1023	210							600 3000 FL150	
				START	PROFILE P2	↗		500ft/min				
113631	23	600ft	1023.	030								
				END	PROFILE P2.							
114053	24	2800ft	1023	035								
				START	RUN	3						
114319	25	2800ft	1023	215	180	187	5.9	4.2			073/10.	
114319	114700	2600ft	descending to stay below cloud									
				END	RUN 3							
114823.	26.	2500ft	1023	215								
				START	PROFILE P3	↗						
114958	27	2500ft	1023.	035	180	190	5.6	<5.3	off			
				END	PROFILE P3							
115410	28.	5000ft	1023	035.								
				START	RUN	4						
		5000ft	1023									
				END	RUN	4						
115918	29.	5000ft	1023	035								
				START	P2 PROFILE P4	↗						
120016	30	5000ft	1023	200	170	185	4.6	-30.6.				
"		climbing cabin to 3000ft										

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 17.9.96 Flight No. A480

Page 2 of 4

VIDEO TAPE

No. A480 #1
Ends 1330

- DFC
- RFC
- FFC

	GPS	INU
Lat.	52°37.15W	52°35.36
Long.	2°31.13E	2°30.01E
Time	120256	120303.

DRS recording to HORACE

HORACE recording to optical disk

SATCOM sending position reports

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		
		Interrupt END PROFILE P4									
120753	31	FL130	—	200							
				RECOMMENCE PROFILE P4 ↑							
120903	32	FL130	—	030							
				END PROFILE P4 /		START RUN		S.1			
121100	33	FL150	—	030							
		cabin stable									FL100 FL120
121603	34			END RUN		S.1 / START RUN		S.2 for zero cabo (low side)			
		FL150	—	030							
				END RUN		S.2					
122021	35	FL150	—	030							
				descending to FL120							
				warp speed to position for stack 2							
				START RUN		6.1		low pitch sailing (1°)			
123623	36	FL120	—	330							
123728	37	End Run		6.1							
				START RUN		6.2		- High pitch angle. (10°)			
123838	38	FL120	—	330							
123939	39.	End Run		6.2							
124156	40	start Run		6.3				- Side slip run. 17° right			FL120
124252	41	End Run		6.3							
124314	42	Start Run		6.4				Side slip run 13° left			

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Video Tape ok?

TIME GMT	EVENT NO	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.			
124730	44	Start	RUN	6.5		side slip R. Wing					19°	
124803	45	End	"	"								
				START PROFILE		P5 ↓		1000ft/min				
124903	46	FL120	—	070								
		descend cabin - 1000ft.										
125641	47	reduce	r.o. descent to 500ft/min.					at	FL40			
		Interrupt Profile P5										
125909	48	3000ft	1025	070								
		Recommence Profile P5 ↓										
125936	49	3000ft	1025	025								
SAWTOOTH			END PROFILE P5 / START PROFILE P6 ↗									
130521	50	50ft	1025	025							5	
		Interrupt Profile P6										
130719	51	1000ft	1025	025								
		Recommence Profile P6 ↗										
130806	52	1000ft	1025					500ft.			500ft/min 600 / 5500 6000	
		cabin pressure const throughout sawtooths.										
		End Profile P6 / START RUN 7 (zero cal)										
131742	53	6000ft	1025	330								
		END RUN 7 / START PROFILE P7. ↓										
132124	54	6000ft	1025	330	180	197	4.4	-23.2				
		END PROFILE P7 / START PROFILE P8 ↗										
133042	55	6000ft	1026	330								
133155		Stop	Video	A480	#1							
133210		Start	Video	A480	#2							

video

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 480.....

Date ...17...9...96.....

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Video Tape
No. A480 # 2
Ends 1630
(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	56' 11.73W	56 12.51N
Long	001' 02.45E	1 00.00E
Time	133557	133622
Status	✓	✓

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
133935	56	5000ft	increase r.o. ascent		to 1000ft/min				
			END	PROFILE P8 /	START PROFILE P9				
134538	57	FL100	—	330					
		START	PROFILE	P9 ↓					
134734	58	FL100	—	040	180	-1.1	c-25.7		144°/12 ^m
135335	59	reduce r.o.d. to	500ft/min		at 4000ft.				
		Interrupt	Profile	P9					
135929	60	1000ft	10	040					
		Recommence	Profile	P9 ↓					
140031	61	1000ft	1027	205					
			END	PROFILE	P9.				
140343	62	50ft	1027	205					1/4.
			START	RUN	8.1	(zero's for instruments)			600
140549	63	600ft	1027	205					
			END	RUN	8.1 /	START	RUN	8.2	
141044	64	600ft	1027	205					
141509	65	Heimann cal	(10 → 15)						
			END	RUN	8.2				
141604	66	600ft	1027						

Video Tape
No. A480 #2
Ends 1630
(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	57'24.25	57 22.50N
Long	105.71E	1'03.40E
Time	143742	143753
Status	✓	✓

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START	PROFILE	P10	↗			
141715	66	600ft	1027	035					
		END	PROFILE	P10		START RUN 9.			
142231	67	3000ft	1027	035					
		ridge	up to	FL29		to clear Cu below.			
		END	RUN 9	/	START PROFILE P11	↗			
142742	68	FL29	—	045	181	7.8	-6.8		
		END	PROFILE	P11					
143422	69	FL60	—	045					FL 6000ft FL 150 +3 ↗ 200 ↘ 100 50
		START	RUN	10					
143553	70	FL50	—	210	180	4.3	-6.7		131/9ms
		END	RUN	10	/	START PROFILE	P12	↗	
144100	71	FL50	—	210					
		cabin pressure increasing							
		Interrupt	Profile	P12					
144603	72	FL100	—	210					
		Recommence	Profile	P12		↗			
144717	73	FL100	—	040					
		END	PROFILE	P12					
145224	74	FL150	—	040					
		START	RUN	11.1					
145335	75	FL50	—	210					
		cabin stable							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A ...480.....

Date17.9.96.....

Page ...4... of ...4.....

Video Tape	
No.	A480 #2
Ends	1630
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	54'07.81N	54'04.15
Long	0'02.13W	0'02.31W
Time	153653	153713
Status	✓	✓

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			END	RUN	11.1 /	START	RUN.	11.2	(zero cal)
145839	76	FL150	—	210	180	-12.1	-25.1	OFF.	150/9.
			END	RUN	11.2	START	PROFILE	P13	
150350	77	FL150	—	210					
		cabin decreasing							
			END	PROFILE	P13				
150827	78	FL200	—	210.					
		Transit		back towards Boscombe.					
1542		descend		to FL100.					
			START	PROFILE	14	↓			
160142	79	FL100	—	240					
			END	PROFILE	14				
161010	80	FL200	—						
161103	81	2300ft							1623
162253		Land		at Boscombe					
162450		Video	OFF						
162937		Stop Recording					GPS	51' 09.85	N E
						bar position	001' 44.65		

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A** 480

Project ACSOE (OKICOA) Date 17.9.96

Tape No A480 #1 User H. RICHES Retention Period 10 years

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
102152	0000	FFC	START RECORDING
103354 → 105015		"	RUN 1, FL100
110045 → 112446		"	PROFILE P1 ↓, FL200 → 50ft
112644 → 113538		"	RUN 2.1, 2.2, 600ft zero cal then run
113631 → 114053		"	PROFILE P2 ↗, 600ft → 2800ft
114319 → 114823		"	RUN 3, 2800ft → 2500ft ⊕ remain below cloud
114958 → 115410		"	PROFILE P3 ↗, 2500ft → 5000ft
115410 → 115918		"	RUN 4, 5000ft
120016 → 121100		"	PROFILE P4 ↗, 5000ft → FL150
121100 → 122021		"	RUN 5.1, 5.2, FL150 (run + zero cal run)
123623 → 123728		"	RUN 6.1, low pitch setting, (+10°)
123838 → 123939		"	RUN 6.2, high pitch setting (+10°)
124156 124252		"	RUN 6.3, side slip, r. wing down, 17°
124314 → 124414		"	RUN 6.4, side slip, l. wing down, 13°
124730 → 124803		"	RUN 6.5, side slip, r. wing down, 19°
124903 →		"	Sawtooths FL120 \ 50ft / 600ft \ 600ft
133155			End of Tape

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A 480**.....

Project **ACS0E (OXICOA)**..... Date **17.9.96**.....

Tape No **A80 #2** User **H. RICHER**..... Retention Period **10 years**.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
133210	0000	FFC	START RECORDING.
→ 140343		"	Sawtooths, FL100 150ft
140549 → 141604		"	RUN 8.1, 8.2 zero cal then run
141715 → 142231		"	PROFILE P10 ↗, 600ft → 3000ft
142331 → 142742		"	RUN 9, FL29.
142742 → 143422		"	PROFILE P11 ↗, FL29 → FL60
143553 → 144100		"	RUN 10, FL50
144100 → 145224		"	PROFILE P12, FL50 → FL150
145335 → 150350		"	RUN 11.1, 11.2, FL150, rather zero cal.
150350 → 150827		"	PROFILE P13 ↗, FL150 → FL200
160142 → 161103		"	PROFILE P14 ↘, FL100 → 2300ft
162233		"	Land at Boscombe
162450		"	STOP RECORDING.

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: AL80

DATE: 17 / 9 / 96

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	/ / / /	/ / / /	
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	/ / X / / / / / / / /	/ / / / / / / / / / /	
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	/ / JN02 / / JN02 / X X	/ / / / / / / / / /	
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	/ / /	/ / /	
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	/ / / / X /	/ / / / X / X	

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A480

Date: 17/1/96

Operator: MT

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G.M.T.		PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	RelT	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit		
10354													
103400	15	0.08											
103600	25	0.08											
103800	37	0.08											
104000	42	0.09											
104200	45	0.08											
104400	40	0.09											
104600	45	0.09											
104800	50	0.09											
105015													
110047	30	0.09										end of Run	
110116	20	0.08										Start Pt from FL200	
110242	25	0.08										FL190	
110341	30	0.08										FL180	
110439	9	0.07										FL170	
110532	7	0.07										FL160	
110626	11	0.08										FL150	
110723	4	0.08										FL140	
110815	18	0.08										FL130	
110914	6	0.07										FL120	
111015	18	0.08										FL110	
111112	33	0.09										FL100	
111210	70	0.09										FL090	
111304	100	0.08										FL080	
111354	75	0.08										FL070	
111527	300	0.09										FL060	
111626	1150	0.11	0.03	5								FL050	
111819	1460	0.10										1000'	
112009	1850	0.09	0.05	5								3000'	
112214	1300	0.09	0.07	5								2000'	
112330	950	0.09	0.2	5								1000'	
112449	550	0.08	0.03	5								500'	
112643												end of P	
112700	930	0.08	0.03	5								Start Run 2 @ 600'	
112900	711	0.08	0.08	5									
113000												end of Run 2.1 2 Start Run 2	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. AL60

Date: 17/9/96

Operator: MLP

Page 5 of 6

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	RelT	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
141605												end of run
141715												start P9
141816	400	0.08	0.8	5								1000'
142007	370	0.08	0.8	5								2000'
142230												3000' end of P and start P9
142800	570	0.09										
142900	180	0.08										
142900	180	0.08										
142942												end of run & start P11
142944	15	0.08										4000'
143137	40	0.08										5000'
143423	40	0.08										FL060 end of P
143554												start P10 @ FL050
143600	45	0.08										
143800	4.8	0.08										
144000	57	0.08										
144100												end of run & start P12
144204	50	0.09										FL060
144303	40	0.08										FL070
144352	55	0.08										FL080
144457	11	0.08										FL090
144559	8	0.08										FL100
144814	3	0.09										FL110
144919	4	0.07										FL120
145018	7	0.08										FL130
145116	40	0.08										FL140
145224												FL150
145337												start P10.1 @ FL150
145400	30	0.08										
145700	12	0.08										
145900	10	0.07										
146030												
146510	10	0.07										
150100	10	0.07										
150300	5	0.07										
150352												start of run and start P13

DATE 17 Sep 96 TI MRF A480NAV AYERS 1/2AIRFIELD B Down 'E' 'F'

AIRFIELD _____

R/W CS W/V 100/14 TEMP +15 QNH 1017 QFE 1002

R/W _____ W/V _____ TEMP _____ QNH _____ QFE _____

WX BLU E NIL 1312 1/270 P1010 C1014

WX _____

ATC CL C/W 1466 3000/4 6501

ATC CL _____

T/O TIME 1022LAND TIME 1623

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1033 ⁵⁺	053	2P	268	232	277	115/18	100	1013	5154.7 ^N 00137.9 ^N	R1
1050									5233.2 ^N 00000.1 ^E	ER1
1100 ⁴⁵	104	5S	253	180	262	066/15	F2000		5226.8 ^N 00102.8 ^E	P1
1113 ⁵⁶									5220.6 ^N 00217.3 ^E	IP1
1114 ²⁶	030	4P	183	177	193	092/31	F060		5221.3 ^N 00219.1 ^E	RP1
1124 ⁴⁶									5248.1 ^N 00241.4 ^E	EP1
1126 ⁴⁴	203	6S	190	181	182	085/16	600'	1023	5246.6 ^N 00244.2 ^E	R2.1
1130 ³⁷									5235.3 ^N 00234.4 ^E	ER2.1/R2.2
1135 ³⁸									5221.3 ^N 00222.5 ^E	ER2.2
1136 ³¹	028	4P	173	186	170	071/26	↑3000?		5220.5 ^N 00224.4 ^E	P2
1140 ⁵³							2750		5231.9 ^N 00232.4 ^E	EP2
1143 ¹⁹	212	3S	203	179	186	072/23	2800		5232.9 ^N 00236.8 ^E	R3
1148 ²³							2500		5219.5 ^N 00220.2 ^E	ER3
1149 ⁵⁸	031	4P	175	182	187	078/24	↑5000?		5218.0 ^N 00222.6 ^E	P3
1154 ¹⁰	029	5P	174	178	190	081/26	5000'		5228.9 ^N 00230.0 ^E	EP3/R4
1159 ¹⁸									5243.6 ^N 00239.6 ^E	ER4
1200 ¹⁶	197	7S	195	168	185	085/20	↑150?		5244.3 ^N 00236.7 ^E	P4
1207 ⁵³									5219.4 ^N 00219.8 ^E	IP4
1209 ⁰³									5218.2 ^N 00223.3 ^E	RP4
1211 ⁰⁰	029	2P	217	181	230	071/18	150		5224.6 ^N 00228.2 ^E	EP4/R5.1
1216 ⁰³									5241.7 ^N 00241.0 ^E	ERS.1/R5:
1220 ²¹									5255.6 ^N 00251.3 ^E	ERS.2
1236 ²³						PITCH DOWN			5347.8 ^N 00121.6 ^E	R6.1

1237²⁶

END

5350.9^N 00116.8^E ER6.1

DISK PROFORMA/NAVFORM

TIME	HGD	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	RUN
1238 ³⁸							PITCH-UP		5353.8 ^N 00112.1 ^E	R6.2
1239 ³⁹							END		5356.0 00108.7 ^E	ER6.2
1241 ⁵⁶							SLIP RIGHT DOWN		5401.9 00108.7 ^E	R6.3
1242 ⁵²							END		5403.2 00113.1 ^E	ER6.3
1243 ¹⁴							SLIP LEFT DOWN		5403.8 00115.0 ^E	R6.4
1244 ¹⁴							END		5405.8 00119.8 ^E	ER6.4
1247 ³⁰							SLIP RIGHT DOWN		5411.7 00136.1 ^E	R6.5
1248 ⁰³							END		5412.3 00139.1 ^E	ER6.5
1249 ⁰³	064	1P	210	182	221	102/21	1200'		5413.5 00144.4 ^E	P5
1250 ⁰⁹							3000'		5429.5 00231.3 ^E	IP5
1250 ³⁷							3000'		5430.4 00232.8 ^E	RP5
1305 ²¹							50'		5447.4 00239.1 ^E	EP5/P6
1307 ¹⁹							1000'		5453.2 00241.4 ^E	IP IP6
1308 ⁰⁶	327	3P	197	181	185	086/22	1000'		5455.8 00239.9 ^E	RP6
1317 ⁴²							6000'		5522.1 00206.9 ^E	EP6/R7
1321 ²⁴									5532.7 00152.9 ^E	ER7/P7
1330 ⁴²	326	3P	195	180	181	102/19	500'		5558.6 00119.9 ^E	EP7/P8
1345 ³⁸									5641.3 00025.7 ^E	EP8
1347 ³⁴	033	5P	222	182	214	150/24	1000'		5647.8 00020.7 ^E	P9
1350 ²⁹									5722.0 00058.6 ^E	IP9
1400 ³¹									5722.0 00055.6 ^E	RP9
1403 ⁴³									5714.1 00048.1	EP9
1405 ⁴⁹	206	6S	181	181	183	130/22	600'	1023	5708.4 00043.4	R8.1
1410 ⁴⁴									5655.3 00031.4	ER8.1/8.2
1416 ⁰⁴									5641.0 00019.7	ER8.2
1417 ¹⁷							3000' 2700'	✓	5639.9 00021.1	EP10/11
1422 ³¹	038	5P	185	180	185	120/24	3100	✓	5654.0 00036.3	EP10/11
1427 ⁴²									5707.8 00052.0	ER9/P11
1434 ²⁴									5726.3 00113.2	EP11

DATE _____ TI MRF _____ NAV _____ 2/2

AIRFIELD _____ AIRFIELD _____

R/W _____ W/V _____ TEMP _____ ONH _____ OFE _____ R/W _____ W/V _____ TEMP _____ ONH _____ OFE _____

WX _____ WX _____

ATC CL _____ ATC CL _____

T/O TIME _____ LAND TIME _____

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1435 ⁵³	207	5S	195	180	196	133/17	F050	1013	5728.5 ^N 00110.4 ^E	R 10
1441 ⁰⁰	206								5714.4 00055.0 ^E	EP10/P12
1446 ⁰³							F100	✓	5700.2 00039.3 ^E	IP12
1447 ¹⁷	038	6f	214	181	214	126/19	F100 ^f	✓	5700.0 00042.6 ^E	RP12
1452 ²⁴							F150		5716.1 00101.5 ^E	EP12
1453 ³⁵	206	4S	227	181	232	140/17	F150	✓	5716.9 00057.5 ^E	R 11.1
1458 ³⁹									5700.8 00039.3 ^E	ER11.1/R11
1503 ⁵⁰							F100		5644.3 00022.0 ^E	ER11.2/P1
1508 ²¹									5627.9 00015.5 ^E	EP13
1601 ⁴²	236	3S	231	180	212	099/13	F100/050		5207.0 00111.9 ^E	P14
1611 ⁰³							2300		5140.6 00131.9 ^W	EP14

A4800

Date: 7/9/96

Hole #	Time	Height	Ch. 100 FT = 13						Ch. 200 FT = 18						Ch. 300 FT = 10						Net
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	Pct	ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	Pct	ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	Pct	
#1	10:49	1600'	422	1405		1241	28.3		428	1406	29.7	1247			396	1324	27.2	1278			300ss n
#2	11:27	600'	420	1532					426	1579					390	1500					NPY cal 600pt
#3	14:43	9800'	420	1505					424	1506					390	1430					ls
#4	11:55	5000'	420	1382		1282			424	1370	12	1297			392	1317		1329			
#5	12:14	14000'	421	1363					426	1330					394	1310					NPY cal 60
#6	13:20	6000'	420	1334					421	1328					387	1211					
#7	13:31	600'	420	1471					420	1622					386	1548					
#8	14:05	600'	420	1629					419	1639					387	1561					
#9	14:23	27000'	421	1494					421	1501					390	1426					
#10	14:36	5500'	421	1368					423	1364					394	1299					
#11	14:44	15000'	421	1397					427	1407					397	1321					NPY cal
#12	15:10	20000'	421	1421		1574	injar		428	1422	45	142	injar		398	110		148	injar		
#13	15:17	20000'	421	1499					429	1472					397	120					
#14	15:26	20000'	420	149					428	1472					399	120					
#15	15:33	10000'	420	146		1240			426	1433		1239			393	119		1260			
#16	15:43	20000'	419	144		Flow's max			423	1471		Flow's max			389	117		Flow's max			#1

A480 17-SEP-96 12:48:21 045 54.23 1.67 FR

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
72.	644.	12.0	212.	-4.6	-24.8	101/10

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A480 17-SEP-96 13:22:57 054 55.83 1.76 FR P

HDG deg 329.	SPR mb 851.	PHGT kft 4.7	TAS knts 196.	TAT C 5.2	DEW C -26.2	WIND deg 182 / 8
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1.50 3.00 4.50 6.00 7.50 9.00 10.50 12.00 13.50 15.00 16.50 18.00 19.50 21.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A480 17-SEP-96 13:04:24 049 54.75 2.61 FR P

HDG deg T 19.	SPR mb 1006.	PHGT k ft 0.2	TAS knots 182.	TAT C 12.4	DEW C 7.9	WIND deg m/s 092/12
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53.16 m GEONE MP 20.79 ppb 03 MF 33.00 55

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

H480

17-SEP-96

11:55:21

021 -- 02.37

2.41 FR F

HDG degT 202.	SPR mb 999.	PHGT kft 0.4	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 12.3	DEW C 7.6	WIND deg m/s 077/10
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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H400

17-SEP-90

11:32:00

021

02.02

2.00 FR F

HDG degT 203.	SPR mb 1000.	PHGT kft 0.4	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 12.0	DEW C 7.7	WIND deg m/s 080/9
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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H400

17-SEP-70

11:30:01

021

02.01

2.03 GR R

HDG degT 201.	SPR mb 1000.	PHGT kft 0.4	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 12.0	DEW C 7.3	WIND deg m/s 080/9
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A480 17-SEP-96 14:03:03 061 0 57.27 0.85 FR P

HDG deg 196.	SPR mb 1016.	PHGT kft -0.1	TAS knots 181.	TAT C 12.7	DEW C 10.1	WIND deg m/s 133/8
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A480 17-SEP-96 14:04:06 062 57.22 0.81 FR P

HDG deg 196.	SPR mb 1017.	PHGT kft -0.1	TAS knots 191.	TAT C 12.8	DEW C 9.6	WIND deg 134/11
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A480

17-SEP-96

14:06:21

063 Ω

57.12

0.71 FR P

HDG deg T 203.	SPR mb 1003.	PHGT kft 0.3	TAS knots 183.	TAT C 11.9	DEW C 9.6	WIND deg m/s 131/9
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FEET - FT 00000 MP 00000 MP 00000 MP 00000 MP

0.00 50.00 100.00 150.00 200.00 250.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A480

17-SEP-96

14:09:00

063 Ω

57.00

0.60 FR P

HDG degT 200.	SPR mb 1002.	PHGT kft 0.3	TAS knots 181.	TAT C 11.8	DEW C 8.7	WIND deg m/s 132/11
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FEET - FT 30.00 15.00 30.00 15.00 30.00 15.00 30.00 15.00 30.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G WIDED	H
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A480

17-SEP-96

14:11:45

064 Ω

56.89

0.49 FR P

HDG degT 198.	SPR mb 1002.	PHGT kft 0.3	TAS knots 182.	TAT C 11.8	DEW C 8.7	WIND deg m/s 129/10
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PRF = 1000 0.00 250.00 500.00 750.00 1000.00 1250.00 1500.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A480 17-SEP-96 14:13:15 064 02 56.82 0.43 FR R

HDG deg T 198.	SPR mb 1002.	PHGT k ft 0.3	TAS knts 185.	TAT C 11.8	DEM C 8.8	WIND deg m/s 133/10
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A480

17-SEP-96

14:14:30

064

56.76

0.38 FR P

HDG degT 198.	SPR mb 1002.	PHGT kft 0.3	TAS knots 182.	TAT C 11.8	DEW C 9.0	WIND deg m/s 125/11	
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 17 SEP 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallels 88°N, Original scale 1:2,000,000

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

A480.TXT

From 15Z 13/ 9/1996 to 15Z 17/ 9/1996

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 28-Oct-1996 14:26

A480 17-SEP-96

P1 FL200-50ft(110045-112446) + Stack 1 50ft-FL150(112446-122021)

A480 17-SEP-96

P5 FL120-50ft(124903-130521) + P6 50ft-6000ft(130521-131742)

A480 17-SEP-96

P7 6000ft-600ft(132124-133042) + P8 600ft-FL100(133042-134538)

A480 17-SEP-96

P9 FL100-50ft(134734-140343) + Stack 2 50ft-FL200(140343-150827)

A480 17-SEP-96

P14 FL100-2300ft(160142-161103)

A480 17-SEP-96 R1 FL100 From 103354-105015 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:31

A480 17-SEP-96 R1 FL100 From 103354-105015 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:31

A480 17-SEP-96 R1 FL100 From 103354-105015 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:31

A480 17-SEP-96 R1 FL100 From 103354-105015 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:31

A480 17-SEP-96 R1 FL100 From 103354-105015 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:31

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 982
Mean 698.103
Standard dev 0.266730
Max value 699.437
Min value 697.831

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 982
Mean 273.290
Standard dev 0.204535
Max value 273.735
Min value 272.882

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 982
Mean 249.006
Standard dev 5.48682
Max value 257.568
Min value 240.869

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 982
Mean 57.5298
Standard dev 5.89068
Max value 66.3898
Min value 44.5836

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 982
Mean 37.1924
Standard dev 13.0070
Max value 68.0531
Min value 5.00032

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 982
Mean 7.106141e-04
Standard dev 3.450284e-03
Max value 1.765686e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 982
Mean 3033.46
Standard dev 3.00116
Max value 3036.53
Min value 3018.46

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 982
Mean 52.2693
Standard dev 0.182543
Max value 52.5554
Min value 51.9146

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 982
Mean -0.847088
Standard dev 0.478188
Max value 7.735176e-03
Min value -1.62852

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 982
Mean 6.02389
Standard dev 0.953047
Max value 7.61842
Min value 3.56921

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 982
Mean -7.13238
Standard dev 0.782165
Max value -5.46365
Min value -8.41070

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 982
Mean -6.229193e-02
Standard dev 0.308654
Max value 0.605202
Min value -1.36103

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 982
Mean 9.39164
Standard dev 0.688625
Max value 10.5537
Min value 7.86382

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 130.184

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 982
Mean 139.419
Standard dev 0.753392
Max value 143.407
Min value 137.891

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 57.4501

A480 17-SEP-96 P1 FL200-50ft From 110045-112446 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:36

A480 17-SEP-96 P1 FL200-50ft From 110045-112446 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:36

A480 17-SEP-96 P1 FL200-50ft From 110045-112446 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:36

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-01-1996 10:14

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-04-1996 10:14

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 10:14

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 09:56

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-04-1996 09:56

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-01-1996 09:56

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-01-1996 09:57

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 1 50ft-FL150 From 112446-122021 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 09:57

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 3336
Mean 830.088
Standard dev 160.320
Max value 1020.88
Min value 570.903

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 3336
Mean 276.161
Standard dev 8.15654
Max value 286.984
Min value 261.907

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 3336
Mean 263.254
Standard dev 16.3558
Max value 281.980
Min value 240.636

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 3336
Mean 42.8733
Standard dev 7.37571
Max value 57.9560
Min value 26.4417

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 3336
Mean 511.828
Standard dev 484.716
Max value 2020.80
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 3336
Mean 0.792675
Standard dev 12.3555
Max value 443.306
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 3336
Mean 1785.47
Standard dev 1672.27
Max value 4584.06
Min value -63.3400

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 3336
Mean 52.5360
Standard dev 0.155681
Max value 52.9282
Min value 52.2884

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 3336
Mean 2.53302
Standard dev 0.123204
Max value 2.85763
Min value 2.32163

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3336
Mean -1.59532
Standard dev 1.38982
Max value 3.31389
Min value -6.91394

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3336
Mean -10.2515
Standard dev 2.58539
Max value -4.40507
Min value -17.1179

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3336
Mean -0.745446
Standard dev 0.901605
Max value 2.54990
Min value -3.71427

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 3336
Mean 10.4694
Standard dev 2.57790
Max value 17.7746
Min value 4.74149

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 81.1546

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 3336
Mean 102.181
Standard dev 10.3998
Max value 121.975
Min value 73.0786

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 37.9488

A480 17-SEP-96 R6 FL120 From 123623-124903 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 12:28

A480 17-SEP-96 R6 FL120 From 123623-124903 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 12:28

A480 17-SEP-96 R6 FL120 From 123623-124903 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 12:28

A480 17-SEP-96 R6 FL120 From 123623-124903 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 12:28

A480 17-SEP-96 R6 FL120 From 123623-124903 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 12:39

A480 17-SEP-96 R6 FL120 From 123623-124903 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 12:28

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 761
Mean 644.494
Standard dev 0.745793
Max value 646.823
Min value 642.360

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 761
Mean 268.154
Standard dev 0.254943
Max value 268.743
Min value 267.612

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 761
Mean 249.934
Standard dev 1.49622
Max value 253.499
Min value 247.709

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 761
Mean 41.9668
Standard dev 3.06937
Max value 48.9607
Min value 35.4989

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 761
Mean 6.87745
Standard dev 5.77801
Max value 33.0096
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 761
Mean 6.377414e-05
Standard dev 1.249838e-03
Max value 2.677634e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 761
Mean 3656.52
Standard dev 8.95237
Max value 3682.17
Min value 3628.59

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 761
Mean 54.0387
Standard dev 0.124051
Max value 54.2264
Min value 53.7986

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 761
Mean 1.32808
Standard dev 0.187922
Max value 1.74351
Min value 1.07364

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 761
Mean -2.913641e-02
Standard dev 6.27753
Max value 5.19757
Min value -19.1019

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 761
Mean -9.86749
Standard dev 2.68073
Max value -0.743126
Min value -15.4369

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 761
Mean -1.18057
Standard dev 1.98981
Max value 1.00547
Min value -7.59348

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 658
Mean 11.1968
Standard dev 1.07732
Max value 16.1003
Min value 9.12765

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 89.8308

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 761
Mean 107.950
Standard dev 10.4956
Max value 119.162
Min value 81.4109

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 27.8012

A480 17-SEP-96 P5 FL120-50ft From 124903-130521 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:53

A480 17-SEP-96 P5 FL120-50ft From 124903-130521 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:53

A480 17-SEP-96 P5 FL120-50ft From 124903-130521 Plotted 9-04-1996 17:53

A480 17-SEP-96 P6 50ft-6000ft From 130521-131742 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:55

A480 17-SEP-96 P6 50ft-6000ft From 130521-131742 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:55

A480 17-SEP-96 P6 50ft-6000ft From 130521-131742 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:55

A480 17-SEP-96 R7 6000ft From 131742-132124 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:56

A480 17-SEP-96 R7 6000ft From 131742-132124 Plotted 9-02-1996 17:56

A480 17-SEP-96 R7 6000ft From 131742-132124 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:56

A480 17-SEP-96 R7 6000ft From 131742-132124 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:56

A480 17-SEP-96 R7 6000ft From 131742-132124 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:56

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 223
Mean 822.645
Standard dev 0.960491
Max value 824.375
Min value 820.489

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 223
Mean 278.070
Standard dev 0.212907
Max value 278.519
Min value 277.704

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 223
Mean 251.128
Standard dev 1.21485
Max value 253.940
Min value 248.157

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 223
Mean 36.6957
Standard dev 1.01175
Max value 38.7685
Min value 33.8902

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 223
Mean 73.6922
Standard dev 11.5140
Max value 105.106
Min value 37.0132

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 223
Mean 1.172214e-03
Standard dev 5.157928e-03
Max value 2.412600e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 223
Mean 1723.28
Standard dev 9.46514
Max value 1744.55
Min value 1706.24

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 223
Mean 55.4573
Standard dev 5.232986e-02
Max value 55.5470
Min value 55.3676

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 223
Mean 2.00119
Standard dev 6.745473e-02
Max value 2.11796
Min value 1.88207

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 223
Mean 2.15452
Standard dev 0.471481
Max value 3.43201
Min value 1.10665

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 223
Mean -14.2186
Standard dev 0.343829
Max value -12.9815
Min value -15.1786

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 223
Mean -0.735733
Standard dev 0.580076
Max value 0.338722
Min value -1.74789

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 223
Mean 14.3898
Standard dev 0.289431
Max value 15.2202
Min value 13.4273

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 98.6164

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 223
Mean 102.425
Standard dev 1.25091
Max value 104.940
Min value 100.344

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 323.226

A480 17-SEP-96 P7 6000ft-600ft From 132124-133042 Plotted 9-04-1996 17:57

A480 17-SEP-96 P7 6000ft-600ft From 132124-133042 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:57

A480 17-SEP-96 P7 6000ft-600ft From 132124-133042 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 17:57

A480 17-SEP-96 P8 600ft-FL100 From 133042-134538 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:00

A480 17-SEP-96 P8 600ft-FL100 From 133042-134538 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:00

A480 17-SEP-96 P8 600ft-FL100 From 133042-134538 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:00

A480 17-SEP-96 P9 FL100-50ft From 134734-140343 Plotted 9-01-1996 18:02

A480 17-SEP-96 P9 FL100-50ft From 134734-140343 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:02

A480 17-SEP-96 P9 FL100-50ft From 134734-140343 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:02

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 10:24

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 10:24

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-01-1996 10:24

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-02-1996 10:23

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-06-1996 10:23

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 10:24

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-01-1996 10:24

A480 17-SEP-96 Stack 2 50ft-FL200 From 140343-150827 Plotted 10-Oct-1996 10:24

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 3880
Mean 797.489
Standard dev 174.659
Max value 1024.88
Min value 465.721

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 3880
Mean 274.179
Standard dev 9.90194
Max value 286.603
Min value 250.120

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 3880
Mean 262.431
Standard dev 14.2588
Max value 283.710
Min value 236.848

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 3880
Mean 43.1599
Standard dev 5.52818
Max value 64.9031
Min value 32.8500

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 3880
Mean 201.506
Standard dev 269.301
Max value 1447.40
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 3880
Mean 0.199275
Standard dev 5.43020
Max value 276.283
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 3880
Mean 2143.29
Standard dev 1856.98
Max value 6094.52
Min value -96.3855

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 3880
Mean 57.0364
Standard dev 0.236640
Max value 57.4884
Min value 56.4649

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 3880
Mean 0.715121
Standard dev 0.258083
Max value 1.24531
Min value 0.259294

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3880
Mean 7.06963
Standard dev 1.31365
Max value 12.1329
Min value 4.10344

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3880
Mean -7.09259
Standard dev 2.00717
Max value -0.877899
Min value -10.6827

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 3880
Mean -0.728676
Standard dev 0.814189
Max value 1.21900
Min value -3.42066

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 3880
Mean 10.1894
Standard dev 1.48793
Max value 14.2034
Min value 6.59625

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 134.907

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 3880
Mean 104.934
Standard dev 10.0436
Max value 124.143
Min value 91.2318

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 201.053

A480 17-SEP-96 P14 FL100-2300ft From 160142-161103 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:12

A480 17-SEP-96 P14 FL100-2300ft From 160142-161103 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:12

A480 17-SEP-96 P14 FL100-2300ft From 160142-161103 Plotted 9-Oct-1996 18:13

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems. Pitch and yaw are only displayed for flight A480, where specific manoeuvres were used to test the response of the NO_x inlets.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument “the fluorescence water vapour sensor”.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm³) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **CO:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3][H_2O]) / (k_5 [M](j_6 + k_7 + [OH]k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + h\nu \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + h\nu \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Laura Cardenas (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters were not recorded on MRF's data recording system and are therefore not available as part of this data summary. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **PAN ECGC's:** Data are not included in this report but will be made available at a later date. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).

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